

Winning Over Recruiting: The Influence of Recruiting and Coaching Investment on On-Field Success in College Football

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Abstract

This study investigates the role of recruiting outcomes and head coach compensation on on-field success in Division I FBS college football. Multivariate regression analyses were conducted to examine the interrelationships among key variables, including head coach salaries and bonuses, win-loss records, and recruiting rankings. The analysis reveals that higher coach compensation is not significantly tied to improved recruiting outcomes, suggesting that attracting elite prospects does not necessarily serve as a financial incentive role in the head coach's compensation structure. In contrast, teams that perform well on the field tend to secure stronger recruiting classes, indicating a reinforcing cycle between athletic success and talent acquisition. These findings provide valuable insights into the interplay among financial incentives, recruiting success, and team performance, with practical implications for athletic departments seeking to optimize resource allocation and maintain competitive advantage.

Keywords: College Football, Recruiting, NCAA FBS, Head Coach Pay, On-Field Success

Despite ongoing criticism of commercialization in college sports—particularly within the National Collegiate Athletic Association (NCAA) Division I Football Bowl Subdivision (FBS), commonly known as Division I-A (DIA)—college football remains a cornerstone of American sports. Its widespread popularity fuels substantial media attention, generates significant revenue, and contributes to both local economic growth and the national reputation of participating institutions (Baad et al., 2007; Baumer & Zimbalist, 2019; Faucon, 2022). The financial rewards tied to on-field success have intensified off-field competition among universities, driving efforts not only to field winning teams but also to maximize revenue streams such as fan and booster contributions, corporate sponsorships, and, most notably, television broadcast rights (Farley, 2024).

Recent conference realignment and the emergence of Name, Image, and Likeness (NIL) agreements have further accelerated this commercialization, creating a high-profile environment that not only elevates institutional reputations but also drives competitive investments. These intensified investments have been illustrated by the skyrocketing salaries of head coaches (Fullerton et al., 2023; Traugutt et al., 2020).

Such financial commitments underscore the critical importance of understanding the mechanisms that drive team success and the sustainable competitive advantage of college football programs. Historically, research on head coach compensation in collegiate sports has been anchored in agency theory, which posits that performance-based pay aligns the interests of coaches (agents) with those of the athletic departments and universities (principals) (Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Jensen & Murphy, 1990). Empirical studies have linked higher compensation to improved on-field performance—often measured in win–loss records and postseason achievements (Colbert & Eckard, 2015; Park et al., 2021).

However, while these studies provide valuable insights into the pay-performance relationship, the direct impact of coach compensation on recruiting outcomes remains underexplored. With recent changes to NIL policies and the expansion of the transfer portal, recruiting has become an even more critical factor in a team's success (Owens et al., 2024), further emphasizing the need to examine its relationship with coach compensation. Given that recruiting is foundational to building competitive teams and sustaining long-term success (Caro, 2012; Bergman & Logan, 2014), this research seeks to investigate whether higher compensation translates into better recruiting classes.

Recent transformative changes in the collegiate athletic landscape further complicate this relationship. The advent of NIL policies now allows student-athletes to profit from endorsements, sponsorships, and other commercial opportunities, fundamentally altering recruitment dynamics by enhancing the personal financial incentives available to recruits (Salaga et al., 2023). Additionally, the establishment of an active transfer portal has increased athlete mobility, enabling players to explore opportunities at different institutions more freely. These developments introduce new variables that could affect how recruiting outcomes are achieved, potentially diminishing the direct influence of coach compensation on attracting elite prospects.

This study aims to fill these gaps by examining the interplay among NCAA head coach compensation, team performance, and recruiting outcomes in Division I FBS football, using data from 2010 to 2023. By assessing whether higher compensation is associated with better recruiting classes and, subsequently, improved team performance, this research offers valuable insights into both theoretical and practical realms. Theoretically, the findings suggest the need for a more refined model of pay-performance sensitivity that incorporates

on-field success, institutional reputation, and emerging dynamics such as NIL and transfer portal influences. Practically, athletic departments may benefit from strategies that extend beyond financial incentives—such as investments in recruiting infrastructure and facilities—to optimize team performance and secure a sustainable competitive advantage.

Literature Review

Agency Theory and Managerial Compensation

The theoretical foundation for examining the relationship between compensation and performance often originates in agency theory, which frames the principal-agent relationship as a delegation of authority from owners (principals) to managers or executives (agents). Jensen and Meckling (1976) famously argued that managers, when not monitored or incentivized properly, may prioritize their self-interests over the principals' objectives. To mitigate this conflict, organizations attempt to design compensation contracts that align managerial behavior with the strategic goals of the firm (Jensen & Murphy, 1990). Empirical studies in the corporate sector have demonstrated a positive correlation between CEO compensation and firm performance, with performance commonly measured through stock returns, accounting income, or market share (Lippert & Moore, 1994; Leone et al., 2006; Rath et al., 2020; Rousseau et al., 2023).

The concept of pay-performance sensitivity describes the extent to which compensation changes in response to fluctuations in organizational performance (Schaefer, 1998). A stronger pay-performance sensitivity is viewed as an effective mechanism to reduce agency costs. However, researchers have also noted that an excessively high level of pay-performance sensitivity can incentivize short-term or risky behavior by agents. Firms often strive for an optimal balance that sufficiently motivates managers

without encouraging detrimental risk-taking (Bloom & Milkovich, 1998). As the following sections show, the fundamental insights of agency theory also apply to collegiate athletics, where head coaches are tasked with maximizing team performance—thereby enhancing institutional reputation and revenues—but operate in an environment with potentially limited oversight and significant information asymmetry.

NCAA Division I-FBS head coaches similarly act as agents working on behalf of athletic departments and universities. In principle, coaches are expected to maximize on-field success, drive ticket sales, secure lucrative television deals, and enhance the overall brand of the institution. Despite these responsibilities, athletic departments may not always possess the necessary information to observe or evaluate the full spectrum of a coach's activities. Indeed, while game-day decisions are publicly visible, the long-term strategic planning, recruiting strategies, and day-to-day decision-making processes remain largely opaque (Orszag & Israel, 2009; Zimbalist, 1999). As a result, it is critical for institutions to create compensation packages that reward desirable behaviors and outcomes. Pay-performance sensitivity should, in theory, reduce the risk that coaches engage in actions that serve personal interests—such as prioritizing personal brand-building or job-hunting over the sustained success of the football program—at the expense of the institution.

Research in sports management has extensively analyzed whether or not NCAA football coaching salaries demonstrate the pay-performance sensitivity evident in corporate governance. While several studies have found a positive correlation between coaching compensation and team success, as measured by winning percentages and bowl appearances (Colbert & Eckard, 2015; Leeds et al., 2018; Lees & Pham, 2020; Park et al., 2021), others argue that higher salaries alone do not guarantee sustained success.

To better align incentives, some institutions structure contracts with performance-based bonuses tied to specific achievements, such as bowl eligibility, conference championships, or high recruiting rankings (Brook, 2021; Fogarty et al., 2015; Langelett, 2003).

Nevertheless, it is important to note that while higher salaries and winning seasons can create a self-perpetuating cycle of success, some scholars argue that the direct effect of compensation on performance can be overstated. Fogarty et al. (2015) emphasize that coaching salaries alone do not guarantee victories, given the multifaceted nature of team success. Injuries, player development, staff turnover, and shifting conference alignments all contribute to the performance equation in ways that compensation packages may not fully address.

Furthermore, the specific mechanisms by which compensation affects on-field outcomes remain only partially understood. This has led scholars to examine additional factors—such as recruiting capabilities, resource availability, and institutional prestige—as mediators in the relationship between compensation and team success (Byrd et al., 2013; Grant et al., 2013; Inoue et al., 2013).

Empirical findings offer mixed but largely supportive evidence. Colbert and Eckard (2015) and Leeds et al. (2018) reveal that teams investing in high-salaried coaches tend to see notable improvements in their winning percentages, suggesting that universities are willing to pay premiums for renowned coaching talents or proven track records of success. This aligns with agency theory, as greater financial rewards are presumed to motivate head coaches to pursue strategies that maximize wins and bolster program prestige.

However, compensation and performance are seldom isolated from contextual

factors such as conference affiliation, recruiting resources, and program history (Lees & Pham, 2020). Programs in power conferences often feature extensive support systems—larger coaching staffs, advanced training facilities, and robust scouting departments—all of which can inflate the performance impact attributed solely to the head coach's salary. In contrast, non-power conference programs operating with smaller budgets typically structure contracts with a higher degree of pay-performance sensitivity, aiming to encourage immediate improvements that can lead to bowl eligibility or conference championships.

Compensation and Recruiting Outcomes

Recruiting is widely recognized as a fundamental driver of success in college football, with the acquisition of top-tier athletes substantially enhancing a team's potential (Bergman & Logan, 2016). Hill and Qu (2019) suggest that better-funded programs—particularly those offering high coaching salaries—are often able to attract blue-chip recruits due to a combination of program prestige, stronger coaching reputations, and more robust recruiting infrastructures. In addition, coaches may leverage their personal reputations and professional networks to recruit top prospects. A high-profile head coach commanding a generous salary can serve as a signal of institutional commitment to athletic success (Colbert & Eckard, 2015), persuading elite high school athletes that they will receive expert training, significant media exposure, and greater opportunities to reach the professional level.

Expanding on the relationship between financial investment and recruiting outcomes, Huml et al. (2019) investigated the impact of new or renovated athletic facilities on recruiting success among Power Five football and men's basketball programs. Using fixed effects regression models, they found no significant post-construction improvements in recruiting rankings,

although modest gains were observed in the two years leading up to project completion. Their findings also highlighted the influence of coaching changes on recruiting outcomes. Similarly, Pifer et al. (2021) examined NCAA Division I men's basketball transfers over five seasons, revealing that transfers—particularly among non-Power Five and in-state programs—led to increased playing time, usage rates, and performance metrics, suggesting a net benefit for both athletes and programs, and emphasizing the need for ongoing policy evaluation.

Further quantifying the impact of recruiting on team success, Bergman and Logan (2016) noted that each five-star recruit contributes an average of 0.306 additional wins per season. With recruiting rankings explaining up to 36% of the variability in team performance, the importance of securing elite talent becomes increasingly clear. Consequently, financial resources allocated to coaching compensation can be seen not only as a reward for past achievements but also as a strategic investment in future recruiting battles. However, despite this widely accepted rationale, there is limited empirical evidence directly linking coaching compensation to incremental improvements in recruiting performance, beyond general team performance measures such as winning percentage and bowl appearances.

Thus, the present study seeks to assess the pay-performance sensitivity for NCAA Division I FBS football head coaches by introducing teams' recruiting performance as a new empirical proxy for team success. This discussion leads to the formulation of the following hypothesis:

H1: Higher compensation of NCAA FBS football head coaches is positively related to better recruiting classes.

Team Performance and Recruiting Feedback Loop

This relationship forms a feedback loop in which past success attracts more high-caliber recruits, further enhancing on-field results. From a resource-based perspective, teams with greater financial, infrastructural, and reputational assets can strengthen their competitive advantage by attracting top athletes. These programs appeal to elite recruits by offering national exposure, experienced coaching staff, and a well-established track record of success (Grant et al., 2013).

Additionally, coaches with winning records can leverage on-field success when recruiting players who hope to compete at a high level and possibly transition to professional leagues. Scholar-athletes often look for programs that will maximize their visibility to National Football League (NFL) scouts and media outlets. In highly competitive conferences, visibility is amplified by national television contracts and significant conference-level marketing. Therefore, programs with a history of strong performances in bowl games and conference championship races generally hold a competitive edge on the recruiting trail (Dronyk-Trosper & Stitzel, 2015; Mankin et al., 2019).

In a similar vein, it is hypothesized that team performance metrics, such as winning percentage and bowl appearances, may impact recruiting outcomes for NCAA FBS teams.

An expected nexus between team performance metrics and recruiting outcomes may suggest that recruiting outcomes can serve as another empirical proxy for team performance. In other words, team recruiting outcomes could be a function of team performance or team reputation in addition to head coaches' personal reputations and networks. Moreover, the adoption of team recruiting outcomes as a measure of team performance for assessing pay-performance sensitivity could be validated.

H2: Better team performance in NCAA FBS football is positively related to stronger recruiting classes

Empirical Research Methods

Sample Selection

The study sample comprises NCAA Division I Football Bowl Subdivision (FBS) teams over the 13-year period from 2010 to 2023, excluding 2020. Data from the 2020 season was excluded due to incomplete and inconsistent schedules caused by COVID-19-related disruptions, which led to game cancellations and modifications across NCAA football. Data was collected at the team-season level to capture annual variations in performance, compensation, and recruiting outcomes. The total number of team-season observations available for this study is 1,775. Three primary sources provided the data for this analysis. Team records, including win-loss statistics and related performance metrics, were obtained from the ESPN website. Head coach salary data, encompassing both base salary and bonus components, were sourced from USA Today. Recruiting rankings were extracted from 247 Sports, a widely recognized authority on collegiate recruiting evaluations.

Only programs with complete data across all three dimensions—team performance, coach compensation, and recruiting outcomes—were included in the final sample. This approach ensured a robust dataset for examining the interrelationships among these variables. Observations with missing or inconsistent data were excluded, thereby enhancing the reliability of the subsequent regression analyses.

Empirical Proxies and Statistical Analyses

The two empirical proxies to gauge NCAA football head coaches' compensation are Annual_Salary and Annual_Bonus. Because certain uncontrollable extraneous factors such as inflation may escalate the amounts

of annual salary and bonuses, we adjust the total dollar amounts of annual salary and bonus by the base year 2010 CPI (Consumer Price Index) issued by the Bureau of Labor Statistics. The dataset includes compensation information for head coaches from a subset of NCAA FBS programs.

To measure NCAA team performances, we adopt four empirical proxies: Winning_Ratio, AP_Ranking, Bowl_App, and Recruitment. The variable, Winning_Ratio, is defined as the percentage of winning games out of total games for each college team and each annual season. The next variable to assess team performance is AP_Ranking. The variable, Ranking, is collected from the top 25 annual rankings in NCAA Division I FBS provided by the Associated Press (AP). So, the college teams that were not included in this annual ranking list are excluded in the analyses with this variable. The third variable, Bowl_App, is defined as a binary variable with 1 if the college football team is invited in one of postseason bowl games and 0 otherwise in each annual season. We adopt this variable as one of empirical proxies to assess team performance, as being invited to a postseason bowl game is often seen as a reflection of superior team performance. The last variable, Recruitment, is a main test variable for our study.

Based on the sample data, we define the variable, Recruitment, for NCAA FBS teams, considering only those ranked within the top 50 recruiting classes. This threshold allows for a meaningful comparison of recruitment strength. Teams that are not ranked in the top 50 recruiting classes are assigned a value of 51. Consequently, the variable, Recruitment, variable ranges from 1 to 51. The two control variables, Public_Sch and Big_Conf are employed to control for the two team characteristics for the analyses. The variable, Public_Sch, is a binary variable with 1 for public universities and 0 for private universities. And Big_Conf has 1 for a college team in power conferences and 0 for non-power conferences.

The pay-performance sensitivity, outlined as the main conceptual framework in Hypothesis 1, is defined as the change in an agent's compensation resulting from a one-unit change in the principal's wealth or performance (Jensen and Murphy, 1990). In other words, the pay-performance sensitivity measures the extent to which an agent's compensation is tied to change in the principal's performance. Because we aim to gauge the pay-performance sensitivity for NCAA football head coaches' compensation in hypothesis 1, we develop the OLS regression equation model (1) by using team performance measures such as Winning_Ratio. In a sense that change in head coaches' annual salary or bonus may reflect change in the past year's team performance as well as this year, we also include a lagged variable of Change in Winning_Ratio in the regression model.

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Change in Annual_Salary}_t \text{ (or Change in Annual_Bonus}_t \text{)} \\ & = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{ Change in Winning_Ratio}_t + \beta_2 \text{ Change in Winning_Ratio}_{t-1} \\ & \quad + \beta_3 \text{ Public_Sch}_t + \beta_4 \text{ Big_Conf}_t + \varepsilon \dots\dots\dots(1) \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, NCAA football head coaches' compensation is highly associated with their personal career reputation (Inoue et al. 2012). Given that pay-performance sensitivity is driven by team performance rather than individual performance or reputation, we seek to eliminate the influence of head coach turnover on the Change in Annual_Salary (or Change in Annual_Bonus) by excluding the years of head coach turnover when calculating the variables. In other words, we measure the pay-performance sensitivity over the tenure of the same head coach (Park et al., 2021). And we replicate the above regression analysis by substituting the variable, Winning_Ratio, with the other two variables, AP_Ranking and Bowl_App as empirical proxies to measure team performance.

Based on the regression equation model (1), we additionally insert our main test variable, Change in Recruitment to see if the annual

change in athlete recruiting outcomes can incrementally change in NCAA head coaches' salary or bonus. Following this discussion, the regression equation model (2) is developed as below.

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Change in Annual_Salary}_t \text{ (or Change in Annual_Bonus}_t \text{)} \\ & = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{ Change in Winning_Ratio}_t + \beta_2 \text{ Change in Winning_Ratio}_{t-1} \\ & \quad + \beta_3 \text{ Change in Recruitment}_t + \beta_4 \text{ Change in Recruitment}_{t-1} \\ & \quad + \beta_5 \text{ Public_Sch}_t + \varepsilon \dots\dots\dots(2) \end{aligned}$$

As discussed earlier, the variable, Recruitment, is defined in the college teams in power conference only. So, the control variable Big_Conf is excluded in this regression model. Since the variable, Recruitment, represents the recruiting ranking of college teams, a lower value of this variable indicates better performance. Thus, the magnitude of the estimated coefficient β_3 is interpreted as the incremental change in the total dollar amount in NCAA head coaches' annual salary or bonus for each one-unit increase (decrease) in recruiting ranking number (recruiting outcome). In other words, the estimated coefficient β_3 represents an incremental pay-performance sensitivity for team recruiting outcome, after controlling for other team performances such as Winning_Ratio. We also considered the lag variable of Change in Recruitment to see if there exists a potential effect of the previous year's recruiting performance on current year's change in compensation.

To test hypothesis 2, we conduct the regression model below. Because we attempt to examine in the hypothesis 2 whether college football teams' reputation established by prior team performances could attract superior athletes in NCAA recruiting process, the dependent variable in the regression model (3) is Change in Recruitment. Since the recruiting market for college football athletes opens and recruiting data is available early each year, we incorporate the previous year's team performance variables as an independent

variable into the regression model.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Change in Recruitment}_t &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Change in Winning_Ratio}_{t-1} \\ &\quad (\text{or Change in AP_Ranking}_{t-1} \text{ or Change in Bowl_App}_{t-1}) \\ &\quad + \beta_2 \text{Public_Sch}_t + \varepsilon \dots\dots\dots(3) \end{aligned}$$

Empirical Results

Table 1 presents descriptive statistics for all the variables. The mean value of Annual_Salary (Annual_Bonus) indicates that the average inflation-adjusted dollar amount of annual salary (bonus) of NCAA football head coaches during the period of 2010 to 2023 is approximately \$1.9 million (\$80,000). The mean value of Change in Annual_Salary (Change in Annual_Bonus) suggests that, on average, NCAA football head coaches' annual salary (bonus) increases by around \$140,000 (\$24,000) per year. Given that the compensation variables exclude the effects of inflation, the finding supports the ongoing public criticism of the excessively high levels of head coaches' compensation. Furthermore, considerable variation in the compensation variables is observed, as indicated by the standard deviation, minimum and maximum values, highlighting the huge differences in compensation amounts among colleges and football head coaches. The descriptive statistics for the team performance variables align closely with our expectation based on the nature of the variables. For example, the values of Winning_Ratio and Bowl_App range from zero to one, as reflected in the minimum and maximum values. Also, the mean values of Change in Winning_Ratio and Change in Bowl_App are close to zero. Given that the variable, Recruitment, represents recruiting rankings ranging from 1 to 50 with 51 assigned to unlisted college teams in the power conferences, the mean value of this variable is approximately 32 which is somewhat higher than the expected average, 26.

As specified in hypothesis 1, the primary objective of this study is to examine if

recruiting outcomes of NCAA football teams as another team performance measure significantly affect head coaches' compensation such as annual salary and bonus. Table 2 presents the estimation results of OLS regression models with the dependent variable, Change in Annual_Salary. Columns 1, 3, and 5 in the table provide results based on the regression equation (1) without the variable of Change in Recruitment. In contrast, the results reported in columns 2, 4, and 6 are based on the regression equation (2) which includes the variable of Change in Recruitment.

In table 2, the estimated coefficients of the change in team performance variables are not statistically significant at conventional levels, except for Lag (Change in Winning_Ratio). The result is qualitatively consistent across both model specifications, whether or not the Change in Recruitment variables is included. This overall finding suggests that NCAA head coaches' annual salary is not significantly tied to current year and prior year's team performance – in short, weak pay-performance sensitivity. As indicated, only the prior year's Change in Winning_Ratio positively affects Change in Annual_Salary and this effect is statistically significant at the 5% level.

As our main test results, the estimated coefficients of both Change in Recruitment and Lag (Change in Recruitment) are negative in model specifications 2 ($\beta_3 = -5,736$, $\beta_4 = -4,081$), consistent with our conjecture that when team recruiting performance is improved – the variable, Change in Recruitment, is decreased – head coaches' annual salary is positively changed. More specifically, the annual salary of NCAA football head coaches' annual salary is increased by \$5,736 (\$4,081) on average for one rank improvement in athlete recruiting in the current (prior) year. However, the effect is not statistically significant at conventional levels (t-value of $\beta_3 = -1.29$, t-value of $\beta_4 = -1.06$) after controlling for other team performance measures such as Change in

Winning_Ratio, rejecting the hypothesis 1. A qualitatively similar finding is also observed in other model specifications. In particular, the results from the model specification 6 show that the estimated coefficients of Change in Recruitment (β_3) and Lag (Change in Recruitment) (β_4) are -6,973 and -4,081, respectively, but they are not statistically significant after controlling for other team performance variables such as Change in Bowl_App and Lag (Change in Bowl_App). This overall finding offers a novel economic implication that team recruiting performance does not have a direct and incremental effect on head coaches' annual salary, either in the current year or the following year when compared to other team performance measures.

Table 4 provides the results from regressing Change in Annual_Bonus on team performance measures. Compared with the results with Change in Annual_Salary in table 3, more significant findings are observed in terms of pay-performance sensitivity. The estimated coefficients for the three variables representing the previous year's change in team performances are statistically significant in both model specifications, whether or not the Change in Recruitment variables are included. Specifically, in the columns, 1, 3, and 5 showing the regression analyses without Change in Recruitment variables, the estimated coefficients (β_2) for Lag (Change in Winning_Ratio), Lag (Change in AP_Ranking) and Lag (Change in Bowl_App) are 254,234, -19,023, and 44,976, respectively, and they are all statistically significant at conventional levels. Given that higher (lower) Winning_Ratio and Bowl_App (AP_Ranking) variables suggest better team performance, the results from all three variables commonly support the expectation that the prior year's improved team performance could lead to a significant increase in head coaches' annual bonus in the current year. However, consistent with the results in table 2, we could not observe significant results in the estimated coefficients of Change in Recruitment and

Lag (Change in Recruitment), providing an implication that change in college team recruiting outcomes does not serve as an incremental bonus incentive relative to other team performances such as Winning_Ratio, AP_Ranking, and Bowl_App. As another potential explanation for this finding, it appears that the compensation structure, particularly annual bonus, for NCAA football head coaches is more inclined to incorporate direct team performances such as winning percentage or ranking rather than somewhat intermediary or indirect measure such as recruiting outcomes.

Table 4 reports the OLS regression results regressing Change in Recruitment on other team performance variables such as Lag (Change in Winning_Ratio), Lag (Change in AP_Ranking) and Lag (Change in Bowl_App). The significant estimated coefficients are observed in model 1 with Lag (Change in Winning_Ratio) and model 3 with Lag (Change in Bowl_App). The estimated coefficient of Lag (Change in Winning_Ratio) is significantly negative ($\beta_1 = -6.051$, t-value = -2.49) at 5% level. Similar findings are also observed in the regression result with Lag (Change in Bowl_App) ($\beta_1 = -2.080$, t-value = -2.24). The estimated coefficient of Change in AP_Ranking is positive ($\beta_1 = 0.055$), providing results that are qualitatively similar to that with Lag (Change in Winning_Ratio). But the findings are not statistically significant. The overall result in table 4 supports the hypothesis 2 and the resource-based viewpoint that college football teams with more and superior financial, infrastructural, or reputational resources are more likely to have better recruitment outcomes by appealing to superior athletes more effectively.

An additional analysis is performed to investigate if and how team recruiting outcomes significantly impact future team performance in the short term. As shown in Table 5, the regression results are somewhat counterintuitive, but carry implications. Specifically, the estimated

coefficient of Change in Recruitment is positive and statistically significant ($\beta_1 = 0.004$, t -value = 3.36). The finding does not support our intuitive conjecture that teams' better recruiting (lower value of Change in Recruitment) could lead to an improvement of future team performance such as Winning_Ratio.

Discussion and Conclusion

The current study set out to examine the relationships among NCAA head coach compensation, team performance, and recruiting outcomes in Division I FBS college football. Two hypotheses were tested: first, that higher coach compensation is positively related to better recruiting classes (H1), and second, that superior team performance correlates with stronger recruiting outcomes (H2). As summarized in Table 6, the findings offer a nuanced perspective on the interconnections among head coach compensation, team performance, and recruiting outcomes.

The analysis revealed that higher head coach compensation is not significantly associated with improved recruiting outcomes. This result challenges the assumption that increased financial incentives translate into an ability to attract elite prospects. While earlier studies suggested that substantial compensation packages signal institutional commitment and enhance a coach's recruiting leverage (e.g., Colbert & Eckard, 2015; Huml et al., 2019), the current findings indicate that the relationship between compensation and recruiting outcomes is more complex.

Several factors may explain why the hypothesis was not accepted despite widespread belief in a positive relationship between higher salaries and recruiting rankings. First, recruiting success is influenced by a multifaceted array of factors beyond the financial incentives offered to coaches. For example, institutional reputation, geographic location, and existing athletic resources can all play critical roles in

shaping recruiting outcomes. A university's historical performance, academic profile, and the quality of its facilities may overshadow the effect of the coach's salary, suggesting that any financial rewards the coach receives alone do not create a compelling enough signal for top prospects.

Second, while higher salaries may help retain high-profile coaches, they do not necessarily improve a coach's ability to recruit top talent. Recruiting is a collaborative process that depends on the entire coaching staff, the strength of the recruiting infrastructure, and the coach's personal network and reputation. Even a highly paid coach may struggle to attract elite recruits without strong institutional support and a well-established program reputation.

Third, the question of causality remains important. Strong recruiting results may reflect the overall quality of a program, which includes factors such as reputation, resources, and performance, rather than being directly caused by higher coach salaries. For example, success on the field often sends a more immediate and convincing signal of program strength to potential recruits. This pattern suggests a feedback loop in which competitive success plays a more direct role in attracting talent, while compensation supports the broader strategy but may not be the primary driver of recruiting outcomes.

Fourth, the complexity of recruiting itself cannot be overstated. Recruiting rankings are determined by subjective evaluations and can be influenced by external factors such as changes in recruiting regulations, the strength of the local talent pool, and shifting market dynamics in high school sports. These variables introduce noise that can obscure any straightforward relationship between coach compensation and recruiting outcomes.

In contrast, the results robustly support the second hypothesis: teams that perform

well on the field tend to secure stronger recruiting classes. This observation aligns with the resource-based view and agency theory as applied to collegiate athletics. On-field success enhances a program's visibility and reputation, creating a reinforcing cycle where winning not only improves current performance but also attracts high-caliber recruits for future seasons. Such a feedback loop underscores the importance of holistic program quality. Success in competitions appears to serve as a more credible signal to prospective recruits than compensation figures alone, suggesting that athletic achievements may play a decisive role in shaping recruiting outcomes.

Finally, the additional analysis offers valuable insights into how team recruiting outcomes relate to short-term performance. Although it was initially expected that stronger recruiting classes would directly lead to improved performance, the results show a positive and statistically significant link between changes in recruiting and future performance indicators, such as winning ratio ($\beta_1 = 0.004$, $t = 3.36$). This suggests that recruiting success may not have an immediate or direct impact, but instead may be influenced by other factors that mediate its effect on team performance.

One possible explanation for this counterintuitive result is the time lag between recruitment and on-field contributions. Newly recruited athletes, especially at the collegiate level, often require time to develop, adjust to the system, and gain playing experience before making a meaningful impact. As a result, immediate improvements in performance may not be observed, particularly for programs that rely heavily on incoming talent. Additionally, coaching strategies, player development programs, and the retention of key athletes likely play a crucial role in shaping performance outcomes beyond raw recruiting rankings.

Another consideration is the dynamic nature of college football, where factors such as injuries, coaching changes, team chemistry, and strength of schedule may moderate the relationship between recruiting and performance. A highly ranked recruiting class does not always translate into immediate success if the team lacks depth, effective coaching, or a system that maximizes the potential of incoming players. Moreover, player departures through the transfer portal or early exits for professional opportunities could diminish the expected benefits of strong recruiting classes.

These findings highlight the complexity of the recruiting-performance relationship and suggest that future research should explore additional variables that may influence the effectiveness of recruitment efforts. Longitudinal studies examining multi-year performance trends could offer further clarity on whether recruiting outcomes have a more substantial impact over an extended period rather than in the short term. Furthermore, incorporating qualitative insights—such as coaching philosophies, player development programs, and institutional support—could provide a more comprehensive understanding of how recruitment translates into competitive success.

Overall, while recruiting remains a fundamental component of sustained team success, its immediate impact on performance appears to be less straightforward than traditionally assumed. These results underscore the need for a more nuanced approach to evaluating the role of recruitment in shaping team competitiveness, particularly in the evolving landscape of collegiate athletics. In summary, the study provides important insights into the interplay among head coach compensation, team performance, and recruiting outcomes in NCAA Division I FBS football. While increased compensation does not directly lead to better recruiting outcomes, on-field success emerges as a key driver of recruiting strength. These

findings contribute to the broader literature by suggesting that the effectiveness of compensation strategies in collegiate athletics may depend less on the monetary rewards themselves and more on the overall competitive performance and reputation of the program.

Implications, Limitations, and Future Recommendations

The theoretical implications of these findings are significant. While agency theory supports the notion that performance-based compensation should align coaches' interests with those of the institution, the absence of a direct link between compensation and recruiting success indicates that other mediating factors are at play. Institutional elements—such as historical performance, overall program resources, and even regional reputation—appear to exert a more substantial influence on recruiting outcomes than compensation alone. This suggests the need for a more refined model of pay-performance sensitivity in collegiate sports, one that integrates on-field success and the broader institutional context into the evaluation of coaching effectiveness. Furthermore, these results contribute to the evolving literature on sport management by challenging the simplistic view that higher salaries automatically yield better recruiting outcomes and instead encourage the exploration of alternative variables like coaching style, strategic vision, and environmental factors that collectively drive program success.

From a practical standpoint, these findings suggest that athletic departments should avoid placing too much emphasis on financial incentives as the main driver of recruiting success. Instead of focusing only on increasing coach compensation, a more balanced strategy may be more effective. This could involve investing in areas that directly enhance team performance, such as improving training facilities, expanding coaching staffs, and upgrading recruiting

infrastructure. In addition, building a strong program reputation through consistent on-field success and reliable support systems can help attract top talent. By taking an integrated approach that considers both performance outcomes and the broader institutional environment, athletic departments can better allocate resources and build a more sustainable competitive advantage.

Several limitations of this study warrant acknowledgment. First, the reliance on recruiting rankings as the sole proxy for recruiting outcomes may not fully capture the complexity of the recruitment process. Additionally, the quantitative approach limits the ability to explore qualitative dimensions of coaching influence, such as leadership style and relationship-building with recruits. Another limitation is the study's exclusion of recent developments related to Name, Image, and Likeness (NIL) policies. Although NIL earnings potential has been modestly linked to recruiting success, current evidence suggests it is unlikely to significantly alter the existing talent hierarchy in college football, with elite and mid-tier programs expected to maintain their traditional positions (Pitts & Evans, 2024). NIL policies allow student-athletes to monetize their personal brands through endorsements, sponsorships, and other ventures while retaining collegiate eligibility (Fortunato, 2025). This transformative shift introduces new financial and career incentives that may influence recruiting decisions and, over time, the competitive dynamics among programs.

In addition, the impact of recent transfer policy changes, particularly the establishment of an active transfer portal, was not considered. The active transfer portal has increased athlete mobility by providing a streamlined mechanism for student-athletes to explore opportunities at different institutions. This development may affect team composition and stability, as well as recruiting outcomes, by enabling athletes to move more freely in search of better

alignment with their academic and athletic goals.

Future research should integrate qualitative methods and a broader range of performance indicators to develop a more comprehensive understanding of these dynamics. Subsequent studies should explicitly examine the impact of NIL by investigating how student-athlete endorsement deals, personal branding initiatives, and associated market dynamics interact with coach compensation, team performance, and recruiting success. Furthermore, future work should incorporate the effects of the active transfer portal by exploring how increased athlete mobility influences recruiting outcomes and alters the competitive landscape in collegiate sports. In addition, research should distinguish between power conferences and non-power conferences, taking into account recent conference realignments, to determine how variations in institutional resources, media exposure, and market dynamics may moderate the relationships among coach compensation, team performance, and recruiting success. Exploring these contextual factors, including conference affiliation and institutional support, could further clarify the mechanisms through which compensation, performance, NIL opportunities, and transfer dynamics collectively shape recruiting outcomes.

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Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	N	Mean	S. D.	Minimum	Maximum
<i>Annual_Salary</i>	1,510	1,934,960	1,580,299	140,000	9,939,286
<i>Change in Annual_Salary</i>	1,025	139,301	496,265	-2,778,079	3,910,590
<i>Annual_Bonus</i>	1,027	80,172	179,900	0.000	1,660,448
<i>Change in Annual_Bonus</i>	622	24,047	171,578	-930,742	1,300,919
<i>Winning_Ratio</i>	1,638	0.520	0.218	0.000	1.000
<i>Change in Winning_Ratio</i>	1,098	0.000	0.202	-0.692	0.690
<i>AP_Ranking</i>	349	13.375	7.357	1.000	25.000
<i>Change in AP_Ranking</i>	142	0.014	7.363	-22.000	20.000
<i>Bowl_App</i>	1,645	0.597	0.491	0.000	1.000
<i>Change in Bowl_App</i>	1,103	-0.006	0.551	-1.000	1.000
<i>Recruitment</i>	845	31.770	16.704	1.000	51.000
<i>Change in Recruitment</i>	633	-0.678	10.843	-49.000	48.000
<i>Public_Sch</i>	1,775	0.848	0.359	0.000	1.000
<i>Big_Conf</i>	1,775	0.512	0.500	0.000	1.000

The definition of each variable is as follows. *Annual_Salary* = Annual salary amount of an NCAA football head coach in U.S. dollars, adjusted for inflation based on the 2010 CPI (Consumer Price Index); *Change in Annual_Salary* = Annual change in the variable; *Annual_Bonus* = Annual bonus amount of an NCAA football head coach in U.S. dollars, adjusted for inflation based on the 2010 CPI (Consumer Price Index); *Winning_Ratio* = Ratio of wins to the total number of NCAA football games played in the annual season; *AP_Ranking* = Final AP top 25 rankings in NCAA Division I FBS; *Bowl_App* = 1 for College Football Playoff team and 0 otherwise; *Recruitment* = A ranking metric for recruiting strength; *Public_Sch* = 1 for public universities and 0 for non-public universities; *Big_Conf* = 1 for power conferences and 0 for non-power conferences.

Table 4: Regression Result - Change in Recruitment

Independent Variables	Dependent Variable: <i>Change in Recruitment</i>		
	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Intercept	-0.064 [-0.06]	-4.075 [-1.48]	-0.073 [-0.07]
<i>Lag (Change in Winning_Ratio)</i>	-6.051 ** [-2.49]		
<i>Lag (Change in AP_Ranking)</i>		0.055 [0.43]	
<i>Lag (Change in Bowl_App)</i>			-2.080 ** [-2.24]
<i>Public_Sch</i>	0.755 [0.65]	4.042 [1.38]	0.772 [0.67]
N	425	108	426
Adj. R2	0.0105	-0.0008	0.0077
F-value	3.25 **	0.96	2.66 *

Figures in bracket denote t-values. ***, **, and * indicate significance at less than the 1%, 5% and 10% using a 2-tailed test.

Table 2: Regression Result - Change in Annual Salary

Independent Variables	Dependent Variable: <i>Change in Annual Salary</i>					
	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6
Intercept	4.085 [0.07]	156,123 * [1.80]	229,521 [0.23]	279,450 [0.39]	4,493 [0.08]	153,677 * [1.76]
<i>Change in Winning_Ratio</i>	-93,164 [-4.95]	64,188 [0.32]				
<i>Lag (Change in Winning_Ratio)</i>	212,293 ** [2.21]	392,278 ** [2.04]				
<i>Change in AP_Ranking</i>			23,267 [1.00]	30,732 [1.08]		
<i>Lag (Change in AP_Ranking)</i>			-8,894 [-0.42]	-6,650 [-0.24]		
<i>Change in Bowl_App</i>					-24,703 [-0.64]	355 [0.00]
<i>Lag (Change in Bowl_App)</i>						27,400 [0.34]
<i>Change in Recruitment</i>		-5,736 [-1.29]	23,363 [0.59]			-6,973 [-1.59]
<i>Lag (Change in Recruitment)</i>		-4,081 [-1.06]	-10,509 [-0.30]			-3,589 [-0.93]
<i>Public_Sch</i>	62,370 [1.11]	115,634 [1.21]	-124,248 [-0.19]	104,508 [0.14]	64,813 [1.15]	119,514 [1.25]
<i>Big_Conf</i>	188,213 *** [4.88]	251,865 [0.33]			185,394 *** [4.79]	
N	657	324	57	48	660	327
Adj. R2	0.04	0.01	0.04	-0.06	0.03	0.00
F-value	7.83 ***	1.73	0.42	0.43	6.25 ***	0.95

Figures in bracket denote t-values. ***, **, and * indicate significance at less than the 1%, 5% and 10% using a 2-tailed test.

Table 5: Regression Result - Change in Team Performance

Independent Variables	Dependent Variable		
	<i>Change in Winning_Ratio</i>	<i>Change in AP_Ranking</i>	<i>Change in Bowl_App</i>
Intercept	-0.023 [-1.02]	4.135 * [1.94]	-0.048 [-0.80]
<i>Change in Recruitment</i>	0.004 *** [3.36]	-0.012 [-0.10]	0.007 ** [2.30]
<i>Lag (Change in Recruitment)</i>	0.001 [1.06]	0.017 [0.15]	0.001 [0.37]
<i>Public_Sch</i>	0.010 [0.39]	-4.412 * [-1.97]	0.004 [0.05]
N	381	88	384
Adj. R2	0.0224	0.0154	0.0069
F-value	3.90 ***	1.45	1.88

Figures in bracket denote t-values. ***, **, and * indicate significance at less than the 1%, 5% and 10% using a 2-tailed test.

Table 3: Regression Result - Change in Annual Bonus

Independent Variables	Dependent Variable: <i>Change in Annual Bonus</i>					
	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6
Intercept	-30,392 [-1.10]	-31,500 [-0.75]	-36,216 [-0.11]	-137,462 [-0.59]	-21,130 [-0.74]	-6,584 [-0.15]
<i>Change in Winning_Ratio</i>	-53,378 [-1.27]	-108,883 [-1.26]				
<i>Lag (Change in Winning_Ratio)</i>	254,234 *** [5.97]	475,459 *** [5.52]				
<i>Change in AP_Ranking</i>			7,539 [0.92]	9,031 [1.01]		
<i>Lag (Change in AP_Ranking)</i>			-19,023 ** [-2.65]	-22,555 ** [-2.80]		
<i>Change in Bowl_App</i>					-3,928 [-0.23]	-13,491 [-0.38]
<i>Lag (Change in Bowl_App)</i>					44,976 ** [2.57]	73,633 * [1.92]
<i>Change in Recruitment</i>		1,015 [0.57]		8,388 [0.76]		-303 [-0.16]
<i>Lag (Change in Recruitment)</i>		-705 [-0.42]		-11,066 [-1.44]		408 [0.22]
<i>Public_Sch</i>	33,982 [1.27]	59,004 [1.31]	18,649 [0.08]	127,595 [0.53]	24,341 [0.88]	38,937 [0.81]
<i>Big_Conf</i>	24,602 [1.51]	11,979 [0.05]			27,564 [1.63]	
N	396	204	46	42	399	207
Adj. R2	0.1001	0.1902	0.0945	0.1732	0.0196	0.0655
F-value	11.99 ***	8.18 ***	2.17 *	2.72 **	2.99 **	1.23

Figures in bracket denote t-values. ***, **, and * indicate significance at less than the 1%, 5% and 10% using a 2-tailed test.

Table 6: Summary of Results

Independent Var.	Dependent Var.		
	Coach Compensation	Team Performance	Recruiting
Team Performance	Significant and Positive (Table 2 and 3)	NA	Significant and Positive (Table 4)
Recruiting	Not significant (Table 2 and 3)	Significant and Negative (Table 5)	NA